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“XAVFSIZ SHAHAR” KOMPYUTER TARMOG‘INI LOYIHALASH

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Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda shahar infratuzilmasining uzluksiz ishlashini ta'minlashda xavfsiz kompyuter tarmoqlarining ahamiyati ortib bormoqda. Ushbu tadqiqotda Cisco Packet Tracer simulyatori yordamida xavfsiz shahar kompyuter tarmog‘ini loyihalash usullari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Loyihalash jarayonida zamonaviy tarmoq xavfsizligi me'yorlariga rioya qilish, tarmoq elementlarini to‘g‘ri joylashtirish va ularning o‘zaro bog‘lanishini ta'minlash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Tadqiqot davomida tarmoqning asosiy komponentlari, jumladan, marshrutizatorlar, kalitlar, xavfsizlik devorlari va boshqa qurilmalar tahlil qilinadi. Tarmoq arxitekturasi, uning segmentatsiyasi va xavfsizlik protokollari bo‘yicha optimal yechimlar ishlab chiqiladi. Cisco Packet Tracer simulyatori yordamida shahar kompyuter tarmog‘ining turli qismlari sinovdan o‘tkaziladi va tarmoq xavfsizligini ta'minlash uchun zaruriy sozlamalar amalga oshiriladi. Ushbu ish natijasida xavfsiz shahar kompyuter tarmog‘ini muvaffaqiyatli loyihalash uchun amaliy tavsiyalar va yondashuvlar ishlab chiqiladi. Natijalar ko‘rsatadiki, Cisco Packet Tracer simulyatori tarmoq dizayni va xavfsizligini sinash uchun samarali vosita bo‘lib, uning yordamida kompleks tarmoq muammolarini aniqlash va hal qilish mumkin. Tadqiqot shahar infratuzilmasining xavfsizligini oshirishga qaratilgan bo‘lib, zamonaviy tarmoq texnologiyalari va uslublaridan foydalanish orqali optimal va xavfsiz tarmoq yechimlarini yaratishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar. Xavfsiz shahar, Kompyuter tarmog‘i, Cisco Packet Tracer Tarmoq loyihalash, Tarmoq xavfsizligi, Marshrutizatorlar, Kalitlar (Switches), Xavfsizlik devorlari (Firewalls), Tarmoq segmentatsiyasi, Xavfsizlik protokollari, Tarmoq arxitekturasi, Tarmoq boshqaruvi, Tarmoq komponentlari, VPN (Virtual Private Network), Tarmoq sozlamalari, Tarmoq monitoring.

DESIGN OF A COMPUTER NETWORK “SAFE CITY”

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Abstract. Today, the importance of secure computer networks in ensuring the continuous operation of city infrastructure is increasing. This study examines methods for designing a secure urban computer network using the Cisco Packet Tracer simulator. In the design process, it is important to comply with modern network security standards, to ensure the correct placement of network elements and their interconnection. During the study, the main components of the network are analyzed, including routers, switches, firewalls and other devices. Optimal solutions for network architecture, its segmentation and security protocols are developed. Using the Cisco Packet Tracer simulator, various parts of the urban computer network are tested and the necessary settings are made to ensure network security. As a result of this work, practical recommendations and approaches are developed for the successful design of a secure urban computer network. The results show that the Cisco Packet Tracer simulator is an effective tool for testing network design and security, which can be used to identify and solve complex network problems. The research is aimed at increasing the security of the city's infrastructure and allows creating optimal and secure network solutions by using modern network technologies and methods.

Keywords. Safe City, Computer Network, Cisco Packet Tracer Network Design, Network Security, Routers, Switches, Firewalls, Network Segmentation, Security Protocols, Network Architecture, Network Management, Network Components, VPN (Virtual Private Network), Network settings, Network monitoring.

Kirish. Bugungi kunda jadal rivojlanayotgan raqamli dunyoda, shaharlar texnologik taraqqiyot va o‘zaro bog‘langan qurilmalarning ko‘payishi ta’sirida chuqur o‘zgarishlarni boshdan kechirmoqda. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining shahar infratuzilmasiga integratsiyalashuvi bilan tavsiflangan aqlli shaharlar kontseptsiyasi urbanizatsiya, resurslarni boshqarish va aholiga xizmat ko‘rsatish kabi murakkab muammolarni hal qilish uchun yechim sifatida paydo bo‘ldi. Biroq, aqlli shahar texnologiyalarining afzalliklari bilan, xususan, kiberxavfsizlik sohasida yangi xavflar paydo bo‘ladi. Shaharlar muhim infratuzilmani boshqarish va davlat xizmatlarini ko‘rsatish uchun raqamli tizimlarga tobora ko‘proq tayanib borayotganligi sababli, shahar kompyuter tarmoqlarini himoya qilish zarurati hech qachon bu qadar dolzarb bo‘lmagan.

“Xavfsiz Shahar” kompyuter tarmog‘ini loyihalash mavzusi bugungi raqamli asrda eng dolzarb hisoblanadi. Shahar aholisi misli ko‘rilmagan sur‘atlarda o‘sib borayotgani va samaradorlik va barqarorlikni oshirish uchun aqlli texnologiyalarni qo‘llayotgan shaharlar bilan shahar tarmoqlari xavfsizligi muhim muammo hisoblanadi. Shahar miqyosidagi kompyuter tarmoqlari xavfsizligining buzilishi jiddiy oqibatlarga olib kelishi mumkin, bu uzilishlardan tortib transport va kommunal xizmatlar kabi muhim xizmatlarga, fuqarolarning shaxsiy hayoti va xavfsizligini buzishgacha. Shunday qilib, shahar tarmoqlari infratuzilmasining yaxlitligi va barqarorligini ta'minlash zamonaviy shaharlarning barqaror rivojlanishi va gullab-yashnashi uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Shahar kompyuter tarmog‘i xavfsizligini qaydarajadaligini bilish uchun, shahar kompyuter tarmog‘ini bir qismi bo‘lgan Bank tarmog‘ida o‘tkaziladi.

1-rasm. BANKning ichki tarmog‘ining tuzulishi.

1-rasm bank tarmog‘ini xavfsizligini va bexato ishlashini taminlash uchun quyidagi protokollardan foydalandi.

2-rasm. Asosiy router.

```
ALOQABANK>en
Password:
ALOQABANK#show run
Building configuration...

Current configuration : 4060 bytes
!
version 15.1
service timestamps log datetime msec
no service timestamps debug datetime msec
no service password-encryption
!
hostname ALOQABANK
!
!
!
enable secret 5 $1$mERr$ZPP4yIRougMgXVlyjTDrb/
!
```

3-rasm. Asosiy routerga kirish.

3-rasmda ALOQABANK tarmog‘ining asosiy routeriga begona shaxslar kirishini oldini olish maqsadida yuqori darajali parol qoyilgan. Ushbu parolni tarmoq sozlash jarayonida kiritilgan va shifirlash algoritimi yordamida shifirlangan. Parolni shifirlashdan maqsad parolni bank tarmog‘iga masul shahslardan tashqari boshqa shahslar bilib olishini oldini olish.

```
username ADMIN privilege 15 secret 5 $1$mERr$ZPP4yIRougMgXVlyjTDrb/
username AXX privilege 15 secret 5 $1$mERr$ZPP4yIRougMgXVlyjTDrb/
!
```

4-rasm. Asosiy router usernamesi.

4-rasmda bank tarmog‘iga masofadan kirish uchun ADMIN va Axborot Xavfsizligi xodimlarining username, darajasi va paroli keltirilgan. Ushbu rasmda usernamelari ochiq ya’ni shifirlanmagan bo‘lsa ham, ushbu xodimlarning

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parollari shifirlangan. Agar buzg‘unchi odam ushub xodimlardan birining usernamesini bilgan taqdirda ham bank tarmog‘iga kira olmaydi, chunki bank tarmog‘iga kirish uchun username va parol kerak bo‘ladi. Bank tarmog‘ida masofadan kirish paroli shifirlangan. Parolning shifirlanishining sababi xar bir xodim o‘z profilidan kirishini taminlash uchun.

```
key chain KALITLAR-BAZASI
key 1
key-string FAYZIMADJON!@#$$%^
accept-lifetime 10:0:0 Mar 5 2024 18:0:0 Mar 6 2025
!
```

5-rasm. Key chain protokolining qo‘lanishi.

5-rasmda key chain protokoli qo‘lnalilgan. Ushbu protokolni qo‘lashdan asosiy maqsad tarmoqqa boshqa router ulansa agar uning ulangan portiga ushbu kalit briktilmagan bo‘lsa u router bankning routerlari bilan aloqa qila olmaydi. Bu protokol xar xil buzg‘unchi shaxslarning tarmoqa ulagan routerlari orqali tarmoqdan ma’lumot olishini oldini oladi. Xar bir bank o‘z filliallari bilan xavfsiz aloqa qilishlari uchun ISPga murojat qilib faqat o‘zlari foydalanishlari uchun alohida tarmoq kanallarini hosil qildiradi. Buning natijasida banklar tez va xavfsiz aloqada bo‘lishadi.

```
!
interface FastEthernet0/0
description O'RTA_SWITCHGA
ip address 1.1.1.1 255.255.255.0
ip authentication mode eigrp 1 md5
ip authentication key-chain eigrp 1 KALITLAR-BAZASI
ip access-group FOR-USERS in
ip nat inside
duplex auto
speed auto
!
interface FastEthernet0/1
description ISPGA
ip address 10.10.10.2 255.255.255.0
ip authentication mode eigrp 1 md5
ip authentication key-chain eigrp 1 KALITLAR-BAZASI
ip nat outside
duplex auto
speed auto
!
```

6-rasm. Port sozlamalari.

```
!  
router eigrp 1  
  network 1.1.1.0 0.0.0.255  
  network 10.10.10.0 0.0.0.255  
!
```

7-rasm. ERGRP sozlash tartibi.

Bu 7-rasmdagi protokol routerlar orasidagi aloqani taminlab beradi.

```
ip nat inside source list FOR-NAT interface FastEthernet0/1 overload  
ip nat inside source static tcp 192.168.13.3 80 10.10.10.2 80  
ip nat inside source static tcp 192.168.13.3 443 10.10.10.2 443
```

8-rasm. Statik ACL.

```
Extended IP access list FOR-USERS  
  permit ip host 192.168.11.100 any  
  permit ip host 192.168.12.100 any  
  permit tcp any any eq domain  
  permit tcp any host 8.8.8.2 eq www  
  permit tcp any host 8.8.8.2 eq 443  
  permit tcp any host 8.8.8.3 eq www  
  permit tcp any host 8.8.8.3 eq 443  
  permit tcp 192.168.3.0 0.0.0.255 host 8.8.8.10 eq www  
  permit tcp 192.168.3.0 0.0.0.255 host 8.8.8.10 eq 443  
  permit tcp 192.168.4.0 0.0.0.255 host 8.8.8.9 eq www  
  permit tcp 192.168.4.0 0.0.0.255 host 8.8.8.9 eq 443  
  permit tcp 192.168.2.0 0.0.0.255 host 8.8.8.4 eq www  
  permit tcp 192.168.2.0 0.0.0.255 host 8.8.8.4 eq 443  
  permit tcp 192.168.2.0 0.0.0.255 host 8.8.8.5 eq www  
  permit tcp 192.168.2.0 0.0.0.255 host 8.8.8.5 eq 443  
  permit tcp host 192.168.11.100 host 192.168.11.1 eq 22  
  permit tcp host 192.168.11.100 host 192.168.11.1 eq telnet  
  permit tcp host 192.168.12.100 host 192.168.12.1 eq 22  
  permit tcp host 192.168.12.100 host 192.168.12.1 eq telnet  
  deny tcp any any eq 22  
  deny tcp any any eq telnet  
  deny ip any 8.8.8.0 0.0.0.255  
  permit ip any any (1808 match(es))  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.2  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.3  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.4  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.5  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.6  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.7  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.9  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.10  
  deny ip any host 8.8.8.11  
ALOQABANK#
```

9-rasm. Foydalanuvchilar uchun ACL.

Bank tarmog'ida foydalanuvchilar uchun ACLni qo'lashdan maqsad, foydalanuvchilarni tarmoqdan foydalanishining nazoratga olish va malum bir chegaralar qo'yish uchun kerak bo'ladi. 9-rasmda keltirilgan qizil ramka ichidagi yozilgan protakollardan maqsad, yuqorida qaysi bo'limlarga ruhsat berilgan bo'lsa o'sha bo'yicha ishlashini va yuqorida keltirilmagan hostlardan boshqasi aloqa qilaolmasligini taminlaydi. Ko'k ramka ichidagi yozilgan protakollardan maqsad tashqi tarmoqda turib ichki tarmoqqa masofadan kirishini cheklaydi va bloklaydi.

```
Extended IP access list FOR-SERVERS
permit ip host 192.168.11.100 any
permit ip host 192.168.12.100 host 192.168.13.3
permit ip host 192.168.12.100 host 192.168.13.2
permit ip host 192.168.12.100 host 192.168.13.5
permit ip host 192.168.12.100 host 192.168.13.6
permit ip 192.168.2.0 0.0.0.255 host 192.168.13.8
permit ip 192.168.3.0 0.0.0.255 host 192.168.13.7
permit ip 192.168.4.0 0.0.0.255 host 192.168.13.3
permit tcp any host 192.168.13.3 eq www
permit tcp any host 192.168.13.3 eq 443
permit ip any host 192.168.13.2
permit tcp any host 192.168.13.7 eq www
permit tcp any host 192.168.13.7 eq 443
deny ip any host 192.168.13.2
deny ip any host 192.168.13.3
deny ip any host 192.168.13.4
deny ip any host 192.168.13.5
deny ip any host 192.168.13.6
deny ip any host 192.168.13.7
deny ip any host 192.168.13.8
permit ip any any
```

ALOQABANK#

10-rasm. Serverlar uchun ACL.

10-rasmda serverlar uchun ACLni qo'lashdan maqsad, serverlardan ruhsat etilgan foydalanuvchilar foydalana olishlar va boshqa mahfiy ma'lumotlar saqlanadigan serverlarga kirishini oldini olish uchun, serverlar uchun ACLni qo'lash juda muhim hisoblanadi. 10-rasmda keltirilgan qizil ramka ichidagi yozilgan protakollardan maqsad, yuqorida qaysi bo'limlarga ruhsat berilgan bo'lsa o'sha bo'limlar serverlar bilan berilgan ruhsat bo'yicha aloqa qilishini taminlaydi. Agar ruhsati bo'lmagan bo'lim serverlarga kirishga urunsa u bo'limga ruhsat bermaydi va bloklaydi.

```
Extended IP access list FOR-HIMOYA
deny tcp any host 10.10.10.2 eq 22
deny tcp any host 10.10.10.2 eq telnet
permit ip any host 10.10.10.2
```

ALOQABANK#

11-rasm. Himoya uchun ACL.

Bu ACLni qo‘lashdan maqsad tashqi tarmoqdagi begona shaxslar ichiki tarmoqa masofadan kirishini oldini olish maqsadida qo‘llanilgan.

```
logging trap debugging
logging 192.168.13.5
line con 0
!
```

12-rasm. SISLOG o‘zgarishlarni saqlash uchun.

SISLOGni qo‘lashdan maqsad tarmoqdagi o‘zgarishlarni serverga yozib olish. Tarmoqdagi o‘zgarishlarni saqlab borish juda muhim chunki tarmoqda kim qandey o‘zgartirish qilganini kiberxavfsizlik xodimi ko‘rib turishi kerak.

```
ntp server 192.168.13.6 key 123
!
```

13-rasm. NTP tarmoqdagi vaqtni serverga bog‘lash uchun.

Bu protokol yordamida tarmoqdagi barcha qurilmalardagi soat bir xil bo‘lishini taminlaydi. Agar buzg‘unchi shaxs o‘z routerini bank routerga ulagan taqdirda ham u router bilan paket almashmaydi, chunki bank routeri bilan buzg‘unchi shaxs routerining soatlari 2 xil bo‘ladi. Serverlarga ulangan va ushbu protakol qo‘lanilgan xar bir routerda vaqt milli sekungacha bir xil bo‘ladi.

1-jadval.

1-ETAJ. ip classless ip route 192.168.5.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2 ip route 192.168.6.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2 ip route 192.168.7.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2 ip route 192.168.8.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2 ip route 192.168.9.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2 ip route 192.168.10.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2 ip route 192.168.11.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2	2-ETAJ. ip classless ip route 192.168.2.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2 ip route 192.168.3.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2 ip route 192.168.8.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2 ip route 192.168.9.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2 ip route 192.168.10.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2 ip route 192.168.11.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2 ip route 192.168.12.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2
---	--

ip route 192.168.12.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2	ip route 192.168.13.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2
ip route 192.168.13.0 255.255.255.0 2.2.2.2	ip route 192.168.4.0 255.255.255.0 3.3.3.2
3-ETAJ.	4-ETAJ.
ip classless	ip classless
ip route 192.168.2.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.2.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1
ip route 192.168.3.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.3.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1
ip route 192.168.4.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.4.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1
ip route 192.168.5.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.5.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1
ip route 192.168.6.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.6.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1
ip route 192.168.7.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.7.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1
ip route 192.168.11.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.8.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1
ip route 192.168.12.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.9.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1
ip route 192.168.13.0 255.255.255.0 5.5.5.1	ip route 192.168.10.0 255.255.255.0 4.4.4.1

Yuqorida keltirilgan 1-jadvalda ichki routerlar bir biri bilan aloqa qilishlari uchun RIP statik mashruzatsiyasi qo‘lanildi. Statik mashruzatsiyani qo‘lashdan maqsad paket yo‘nalishini boshqarish va nazorat qilishdan iborat. Ushbu qilingan mashruzatsiyada paketlar soat strelkasi bo‘yicha paket almashishadi.

14-rasm. RIP statik aloqa jarayoni.

14-rasmda yuqorida keltirilgan 1-jadvalga misol tariqasida ichki tarmoqdagi paketlar almashuvi ko‘rsatilgan.

15-rasm. VTP foydalanuvchilar o'rtasida aloqa jarayoni.

Yuqorida keltirilgan 15-rasmda VTP mashruzatsiyasi qo'lanilgan. Bu mashruzatsiyani qo'lashdan maqsad ichki tarmoq ichida alohida tarmoq qurish. Ushbu tarmoqni qurishdan masad xavfsizlik xodimlarini bir birlari bilan almashish tezligini va xvfsizligini oshirish maqsadida. 14-rasmdagi yashil ramka ichida AX va ADMIN xodimlari ko'rsatilgan, qizil ramka ichida ularni paket almashishi qandey amalga oshishi haqida jadval keltirilgan.

Xulosa. Biz Cisco Packet Tracer simulyatoridan foydalangan holda "Xavfsiz shahar" tarmog'ini loyihaladik va buni shahar tarmog'iga kiruvchi bank tarmog'ida sinovdan o'tkazdik. Biz yaratgan tarmoq sinov jarayoni mobaynida xar xil tarmoqni buzib kirish yo'lari bilan sinab ko'rildi va sinovdan a'lo darajada o'tdi. Cisco Packet Tracer simulyatori yordamida yaratilgan virtual tarmoqni real tarmoq maqsadida foydalanish uchun uchun qo'lansa ham o'z samarasini ko'rsatadi va "Xavfsiz shahar" tarmog'ini aloq xavfsizligini taminlab bera oladi.

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